

Synthesis of Heterogeneous Metal Oxide Nanocatalysts and Their Applications in Biodiesel Production from Algal Oil: A Review

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ABSTRACT:

The need for sustainable and renewable energy sources is being given more attention to alternative sources of energy, such as those that do not rely on fossil fuels. Algal oil, derived from microalgae, is a required feedstock due to its high lipid content and extended growth rate. This review focuses on the synthesis of nano-heterogeneous catalysts and their application in biodiesel production from algal oil. Nano-catalysts provide enhanced surface area, superior activity, and recyclability, making them highly efficient for transesterification processes. The review explores different methods in synthesis of nano-catalysts by coprecipitation, hydrothermal, sol-gel, green method, impregnation method and combustion techniques. The Sol-gel method was found better for heterogeneous nano-catalyst synthesis. The role of different metal oxides like CaO, MgO, as well as metal oxide-supported nanostructures and functionalized materials in catalysis is critically analysed. The development of nano-heterogeneous catalysts in biodiesel production from algal oil offers a green and efficient route toward future energy solutions. This review uniquely highlights that sustainability and future energies align well with current global priorities. The previous reviews were lacking in such aspect.

Keywords: Biodiesel, Algal oil, Nano-catalysts, Heterogeneous catalysis, Renewable energy, Transesterification

INTRODUCTION:

Biodiesel is obtained from naturally occurring sources; hence, it is a biodegradable and non-hazardous biofuel produced via the transesterification of triglyceride-rich feedstocks with

short-chain alcohols. Biodiesel consists primarily of Fatty Acid Methyl Esters (FAMES). FAME compete with petroleum fuels and biodiesel exhibits reduced particulate matter, carbon monoxide, and sulphur oxide emissions while consisting of similar energy contents and compatibility with existing diesel engines (Wan Oswan et al, 2024). It is sustainable and has lower life-cycle greenhouse gas emissions. Nowadays, it's a better alternative fuel at the global level. Traditionally, biodiesel production was heavily dependent on edible vegetable oils such as soybean, groundnut and palm oil. However, large-scale use of these feedstocks introduces concerns regarding food security, land-use change, and price volatility for farmers (Gincy Marina Mathew et al, 2021). The high cost and food-versus-fuel concerns associated with edible oils necessitate the exploration of non-edible, sustainable and high-lipid-yielding feedstocks such as microalgae.

Microalgae are a better third-generation biodiesel feedstock with distinct advantages over terrestrial crops. They have significant lipid contents ranging from 20% to over 61% of dry biomass, depending on species and cultivation conditions (David A. Wood, 2021). Besides this, microalgae grown in brackish or water reservoirs reduce freshwater demand and avoid competing with agricultural land (Abhispa Bora.,et al., 2024). The transesterification reaction converts triglycerides present in algal oil into FAMES by reacting them with methanol in the presence of a homogeneous and heterogeneous catalyst. The drawbacks of such a process is soap formation, difficulty in separation, and wastewater generation. Homogeneous acid catalysts can process feedstocks with higher Free Fatty Acid (FFA) content but require extended reaction times and more methanol-to-oil ratios. Homogeneous base catalysts can also process feedstocks with higher free fatty acids. A homogeneous catalyst cannot be recovered after the completion of the reaction, and this is the major drawback of homogeneous catalysts. Due to this homogeneous catalyst is not an option for biodiesel production (Alahmar et al., 2025 and Bahadoran et al., 2022).

Heterogeneous Nano catalysts are solid catalysts structured at the nanometer scale, offering exceptionally high surface-to-volume ratios, enhanced active site accessibility, and tunable physicochemical properties. They can be designed from metal oxides (e.g., CaO, MgO, SrO, CuFe₂O₄ and ZnO), mixed oxides, supported catalysts, and magnetic nanostructures (Patil et al.,2025). Magnetic nano-catalysts, in particular, enable easy recovery and reuse via magnetic separation, thereby reducing operational costs and improving sustainability.

The use of heterogeneous Nano catalysts in the preparation of biodiesel from algal oil enhances transesterification efficiency, reduces reaction times, and minimises waste generation. However, challenges such as nanoparticle leaching, catalyst deactivation, scalability of synthesis methods, and environmental safety will be noticed for commercial purposes.

Synthesis of Heterogeneous Nanocatalysts:

The efficiency of heterogeneous Nano catalysts in biodiesel production is largely determined on the basis of their physicochemical parameters such as surface area, pore structure, crystallinity, particle size, and active site distribution. These properties are largely affected by the synthesis method used for the synthesis of a heterogeneous nano-catalyst. This section has written the most widely used synthesis techniques for the synthesis of metal oxide nano catalyst, which is further employed for the production of biodiesel. The synthesis techniques of heterogeneous nanocatalyst are represented as shown in fig:1.

Synthesis Techniques of Heterogeneous Nano catalysts

Fig: 1 Showing the flow chart for the synthesis technique of heterogeneous nanocatalysts

Some of the methods of synthesis techniques are discussed below. also, Table:1: Summary of synthesis method chart of different techniques of nanocatalysts. The comparative data in Table: 1 show that the sol–gel synthesis route yields superior heterogeneous nanocatalysts compared with the other methods discussed.

1. Physical Methods:

Sol-Gel Method :

The Sol-gel method is a wet-chemical approach involving the hydrolysis and polycondensation of metal alkoxides or metal salts, resulting in the formation of a colloidal suspension (sol) that consequently evolves into a three-dimensional network (gel). The process allows precise control over particle size, surface area, and porosity, which are critical for catalytic activity (Steinbach et al.,2023). For example, CaO and MgO nanocatalysts synthesized via sol-gel exhibit high transesterification activity due to their uniform pore distribution and large active surface area (Asfaw Adeko Tigro et al.,2025). This method has several advantages such as high purity and homogeneity of catalyts. This method also helps to controlled particle size and morphology. It can synthesise multi-component or doped catalyts. The most crucial drawback of sol-gel methods is high cost precursors.

2. Chemical Methods:

Co-Precipitation Method: Co-precipitation involves the simultaneous precipitation of more than one metal hydroxide from an aqueous solution upon the addition of a precipitating agent like NaOH and NH₄OH. This method is economically affordable, scalable, and widely used for preparing mixed oxide nanocatalysts such as Fe₃O₄, NiFe₂O₄, Sb₂O₃ and CuFe₂O₄ (Magar et al 2024). The crucial parameters affecting catalyst properties include pH, rate of precipitation, temperature, and ageing time. Post-Synthesis calcination enhances crystallinity and stabilises active phases. This method has advantages over other methods, such as a Simple and scalable process, as well as being suitable for a multi-metal system with low reaction temperature. This method has limitations, as particle agglomeration may reduce the surface area. This method also requires post-calcination for phase stability.

Hydrothermal and Solvothermal Methods: Hydrothermal synthesis is performed in a sealed autoclave at elevated temperatures and pressures, using water as the solvent. In solvothermal methods, organic solvents are employed instead. These methods promote the formation of well-crystallized nanoparticles with controlled size, shape, and phase composition (Tayade et al., 2023). It is important that Zinc oxide and TiO₂ nanocatalysts produced via hydrothermal treatment have demonstrated enhanced transesterification activity due to their high surface reactivity and defect-rich structures. This method provides Excellent control over crystallinity

and morphology of the nanocatalyst. It can synthesise metastable phases. It is an environmentally friendly water-based process. The limitation of this process is that it requires specialised equipment. Its batch size is limited by autoclave volume.

Biological (Green) Methods: Biological (Green) synthesis methods employ environmentally benign routes that utilise plant extracts, microorganisms, or biodegradable polymers as suppressing and stabilising agents. This approach minimises hazardous by-products and aligns with sustainable chemistry principles (Arif et al., 2023). Plant-derived polyphenols, flavonoids, and proteins can suppress metal ions to nanoparticles while simultaneously stabilising them. For example, magnetic Fe₃O₄ nanocatalysts synthesised using tea extract have been successfully utilised for biodiesel production, offering an eco-friendly preparation method and facilitating easy recovery. It has the advantage of low air pollution and no requirement for toxic chemicals. This is the cost-effective method. The limitation of this method is variability in green precursor composition. This method has limited scope for reproducibility.

Table:1 Summary of synthesis method different techniques of nanocatalysts

Method	Control Over Properties	Cost	Scalability	Environmental Impact
Sol-Gel	Most	Most	Moderate	Moderate
Co-Precipitation	Moderate	little	High	Little-Moderate
Hydrothermal	High	Modern Low-	Moderate little	Moderate
Green synthesis	Little-Moderate	Little	little-Moderate	Very little

3. Types of Heterogeneous Nanocatalysts for Algal Biodiesel

The choice of nanocatalyst type is a critical factor influencing transesterification efficiency, biodiesel yield, catalyst stability, and process economics. Heterogeneous nanocatalysts applied for algal biodiesel production can be broadly classified into metal oxides, mixed oxides, supported catalysts, and magnetic nanocatalysts. Each category offers unique structural and chemical properties that govern catalytic performance.

3.1. Metal Oxide Nanocatalysts: Metal oxides are tremendously applied in biodiesel production leads to their strong basicity, thermal stability, and relatively low cost. Common

examples include Calcium oxide (CaO), Magnesium oxide (MgO) and Zinc oxide (ZnO). CaO nanoparticles are particularly effective for methanol-based transesterification due to their high basic strength, although they may suffer from leaching in the presence of moisture and CO₂. ZnO nanoparticles show both basic and amphoteric properties, enabling catalysis in feedstocks with moderate free fatty acid (FFA) levels. Metal oxide has high surface area and active basic sites with low toxicity and abundance of raw materials. It has limited susceptibility to deactivation from moisture/CO₂ also limited tolerance to very high free fatty acid content (Rakesh Kumar Sharma et al., 2023).

Fig: 2 showing the mind map concept for the metal oxide Nano-catalysts for biodiesel production

3.2 Mixed Oxide Nanocatalysts: Mixed oxides are prepared by combining multi metal oxides, which can yield mutual effects such as to increase basicity, thermal stability, and improved spread of active sites. The mixed metal oxide like CaO-MgO, ZnO-Al₂O₃ and MgO-TiO₂ mixed oxides have shown superior reusability and stability compared to single oxides, with reduced leaching and higher resistance to saponification (Xia et al., 2022 and Basker et al., 2017).

Fig: 3 showing the mind map concept for the mixed metal oxide Nano-catalysts for biodiesel production

3.3. Supported Nanocatalysts: In supported catalysts, active nanocatalyst particles are spread over a high-surface-area support material such as silica (SiO₂), alumina (Al₂O₃), activated carbon, or zeolites. The support improves catalyst dispersion, mechanical strength, and accessibility of active sites. The material like K₂O/SiO₂ and CaO/Al₂O₃ systems have been widely studied for biodiesel synthesis. Zeolite-supported catalysts can also provide shape-selective catalysis, beneficial for feedstocks with complex lipid profiles. The supported nanocatalysts enhanced structural stability and adaptable to various reaction stability. The drawback is that, it has possible leaching of active sites from the support and higher cost of some support materials (Hosseini et al.,2022)

Magnetic Nanocatalysts: Magnetic nanocatalysts, such as Fe₃O₄, CoFe₂O₄, CuFe₂O₄ and magnetically modified CaO or ZnO, enable easy recovery and reuse via magnetic separation. This reduces the need for filtration or centrifugation, lowering energy and operational costs. Fe₃O₄@CaO core-shell nanostructures combine high basicity with magnetic retrievability, achieving >95% biodiesel yield under optimized conditions (Corrales-Pérez et al.,2024). Magnetic catalysts can be synthesized through coprecipitation, solvothermal, or sol-gel routes, with subsequent coating or doping to enhance catalytic properties. It is Simple magnetic separation and recycling and reduced catalyst loss during recovery. It has potential integration into continuous processes. It has also

potential reduction in surface area due to magnetic core coating and thermal stability limitations for some magnetic phases (Hussain et al., 2025)

3.4. Extraction of oil from Algae: The Soxhlet extraction method is used for extracting oil from dried algae collected from water reservoirs. This method for algal oil recovery in lab-scale biodiesel research, offering dependable results for triglyceride extraction. However, its limitations—especially in terms of time, solvent use, and the inability to fully recover polar lipids (triglycerides). It highlights the importance of method selection based on lipid class and sustainability goals (Banerjee et al. 2019).

3.5 Reaction Mechanism Overview: In nanocatalyst-mediated transesterification, the mechanism involves the activation of methanol and triglyceride molecules on catalyst active sites (Patil et al., 2025).

- i. **Adsorption of Methanol** – The methanol molecule adsorbs onto basic sites of heterogeneous Nano-catalyst, forming alkoxide ions.
- ii. **Triglyceride Activation** – Triglyceride molecules of oil feedstock adsorb on the catalyst surface, aligning for nucleophilic attack.
- iii. **Nucleophilic Attack** – The basic alkoxide ion attacks the carbonyl carbon of the triglyceride, forming a tetrahedral intermediate.
- iv. **Product Formation** – Fatty acid methyl ester (FAME) and diglyceride are released, with subsequent steps yielding monoglyceride and glycerol.

Fig. 4: Transesterification reaction mechanism using copper ferrite (magnetic nanocatalyst) as a heterogeneous catalyst

Summary Table:2: showing a comparison of different catalysts for the production of biodiesel

Type	Example	Key Properties	Advantages	Limitations
Metal Oxide	CaO, MgO, ZnO	Strong basicity, thermal stability	Affordable & High activity	Moisture/CO ₂ Low sensitivity
Mixed	CaO-MgO,	Synergistic effects,	High reusability,	More complex
Oxides Supported	ZnO-Al ₂ O ₃ CaO/Al ₂ O ₃ K ₂ O/SiO ₂	enhanced stability High surface area, Good dispersion	reduced leaching Structural stability, High activity	Synthesis Possible leaching From support
Magnetic	Fe ₃ O ₄ @CaO, CoFe ₂ O ₄ and CuFe ₂ O ₄	Magnetic Separation, Reusability	Easy recovery, low loss	Lower surface area in some designs

4. Catalytic Performance and Reusability

The catalytic performance of heterogeneous nanocatalysts in algal biodiesel production is typically evaluated in terms of biodiesel yield, reaction rate, reaction conditions, and reusability. The parameters are influenced by catalyst composition, surface properties, synthesis method, and operating conditions (Patil, N.M., Patil, M.R., Marathe, Y.V. *et al.*2025).

Performance Parameters:

The following are the important parameters

- **Biodiesel Yield (%)** – The extent of fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) obtained relative to the total triglyceride content (Farooq Anwar et al., 2023).
- **Reaction Time** – Time required to achieve maximum yield under given conditions (Digamber sing et al.,2020).

- **Methanol-to-Oil Molar Ratio** – An excess of methanol drives the reaction forward but requires downstream recovery (Salaheldeen, M., et al).
- **Catalyst Loading (wt %)** – Amount of catalyst relative to the oil mass, affecting active site availability (Mohammed Takase et al., 2022).
- **Reaction Temperature** – It affects molecular collisions and reaction kinetics.

Studies report that nanostructured CaO catalysts can achieve > 95% FAME yield within 60-120 min at moderate temperatures (55-65 °C) using methanol-to-oil molar ratios of 6:1 to 12:1. Similarly, magnetic Fe₃O₄ @CaO nanocatalysts have achieved yields above 96% with above 96% with simplified recovery via magnetic separation (Xia et al.,2022).

4.1 Factors Affecting Performance: (Chozhavendhan et al.,2020)

1. **Surface Area and Porosity** - Greater surface areas provide more active sites, increasing reaction rates.
2. **Basicity/Acidity** – Strong basic sites promote methanol activation, while acid sites can esterify free fatty acids, making bifunctional catalysts suitable for high free fatty acid algal oils.
3. **Particle Size** – Nanoscale particles improve mass transfer and reduce diffusion limitations.
4. **Catalyst Stability** – Resistance to sintering, leaching, and fouling ensures long-term activity.
5. **Alcohol Type** – Methanol is the most common due to low cost and high reactivity, but ethanol is also considered for greener processing despite slower kinetics (Krishna Prasad Shrestha et al.,2025).

4.2 Reusability and Deactivation

Reusability is an important, affordable and environmental benefit of heterogeneous nanocatalysts. After each reaction cycle, catalysts are recovered (by filtration, centrifugation, or magnetic separation), washed, dried, and reused.

- **Typical Stability** – Most nanocatalysts retain >85% of their initial activity for 4-6 cycles.
- **Deactivation Mechanisms include:**
- **Active Site Leaching** – Dissolution of metal species into the reaction mixture.

- **Surface Fouling** – Deposition of organic residues or glycerol on active sites.
- **Sintering** – Growth of nanoparticles at high temperatures, reducing surface area.
- **Moisture/CO₂ Adsorption** – Conversion of basic oxides into carbonates or hydroxides, reducing basicity.

By using Fe₃O₄@CaO nanocatalysts maintained 92% of their practical yield after 6 cycles, with deactivation attributed mainly to carbonate formation on the surface (Patil et al., 2025).

4.3 Strategies to Improve Reusability:

- **Surface Modification:** Coating nanoparticles with inert layers (e.g., silica) to prevent leaching.
- **Bifunctional Catalysts:** Combining both acidic and basic sites in metal oxide to process both triglycerides and free fatty acids together.
- **Regeneration Treatment:** Calcination is done at higher temperatures solvent washing to remove surface deposits.
- **Magnetic Recovery:** A Magnetic Nano-catalyst has been used in the production of biodiesel.

5. Challenges and Future Prospects:

The application of heterogeneous Nano-catalysts in the conversion of algal oil into biodiesel offers clear benefits in terms of catalyst recovery, process sustainability, and biodiesel quality. However, further methods can be developed from an industrial point of view.

5.1 Technical Challenges:

1. Catalyst Deactivation:

- Nano-catalysts are developed for the **leaching of active components**, particularly in methanol-rich environments or when processing oils with high moisture and free fatty acid content. Surface available from glycerol and other by-products reduces active site availability over repeated cycles. Adsorption of CO₂ and H₂O can transform basic oxides (e.g., CaO) into carbonates or hydroxides, reducing catalytic basicity (Gimbun et al., 2025).

2. Reaction Optimisation:

- Optimisation of parameters like temperature, alcohol-to-oil ratio, and catalyst loading, very depending on algal species and oil composition. High alcohol-to-oil ratios improve yield but complicate recovery and increase energy consumption.

3. Feedstock variability

- Lipid content and composition in algal biomass vary with species, cultivation medium, and harvesting conditions (Morales et al.,2021).
- High-FFA algal oils require catalysts with both acid and base sites or pre-treatment to avoid saponification.

5.2. Economic Challenges

1. Nano-catalyst Synthesis Cost: The synthesis methods, like sol-gel and hydrothermal methods, require costly precursors and energy-intensive processing. Major scale production of biodiesel demands cost reduction through cheaper precursors.

2. Process Integration: It requires scaling up for algal cultivation, oil extraction, and transesterification into a continuous process. Current pilot plants remain major intensive, with uncertain economic viability compared to fossil diesel.

6. Conclusion:

The synthesis of heterogeneous nano-catalysts is intended as a promising approach to overcoming the limitations of conventional catalysts in biodiesel production from algal oil. Their unique physicochemical properties, such as high surface area, tunable porosity, and tailored active sites, contribute to enhanced catalytic efficiency, reusability, and ease of separation. Magnetic Nano-catalysts, mixed metal oxides, and supported catalysts, in particular, have shown remarkable performance in transesterification reactions, achieving high biodiesel formation under mild conditions while reducing recovery processing costs.

Besides these advantages, several challenges remain before large-scale implementation can be realised. The scalability of nano-catalyst synthesis methods, prevention of active site leaching, and mitigation of potential nanoparticle toxicity in aquatic and terrestrial environments are critical issues requiring urgent attention. Additionally, the variability in lipid profiles of different algal species demands adaptable catalytic systems capable of maintaining

high performance across diverse feedstocks. From an economic perspective, the development of low-cost, green synthesis methods for Nano-catalysts is a prominent option.

In conclusion, heterogeneous Nano-catalysts hold significant potential to transform algal biodiesel production into a sustainable, cost-effective, and scalable technology. By addressing current technical and economic barriers through innovative material design and process integration, the role of heterogeneous nanomaterials in renewable energy can be further expanded, contributing to the transition toward a low-carbon, sustainable energy future.

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References:

- 1) Arif, Z.; Sethy, N. K.; Mishra, P.; Kumar, P.,(2023). Green Synthesis of Nanomaterials from Biomass Waste for biodiesel production. In *NanoBioenergy: Application and Sustainability Assessment*, Springer,211-234. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-6234-9_8.
- 2) Alahmar, N.M., Azelee, N.I.B.W. & Toemen, S. (2025), Efficient biodiesel production from waste cooking oil using a bifunctional Ce/Mn/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalysts. *Sci Rep* **15**, 352 . <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-82845-2>.
- 3) Anita K Tawade, Ajay P Khairnar, Jayashri V Kamble, Akash R Kadam, Kiran Kumar K Sharma, Anil A Powar, Vijay S Patil, Manohar R Patil, Sawanta S Mali, Chang Kook Hong, Shivaji N Tayade (2023), Designing a TiO₂-MoO₃-BMIMBr nanocomposite by a solvohydrothermal method using an ionic liquid aqueous mixture: an ultra-high sensitive acetaminophen sensor *RSC Adv.*, **13**, 21283-21295, DOI: [10.1039/D3RA02611F](https://doi.org/10.1039/D3RA02611F) .
- 4) Abhispa Bora, Angelin Swetha Thondi Rajan, Kumar Ponnuchamy, Govarthan Muthusamy, Arun Alagarsamy., (2024). Microalgae to bioenergy production: Recent advances, influencing parameters, utilization of wastewater – A critical review,*Science of The Total Environment*,946,174230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.174230>.
- 5) Asfaw Adeko Tigro, Sintayehu Mekuria Hailegiorgis, Ali Shemsedin Reshad., (2025). Heterogeneous alkaline calcium oxide nano-catalyst supported on porous materials for the transesterification reaction: A review, *27*,105912. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2025.105912>.

- 6) Bahadoran, A.; Ramakrishna, S.; Oryani, B.; Al-Keridis, L. A.; Nodeh, H. R.; Rezaia, S. J. F.,(2022). Biodiesel production from waste cooking oil using heterogeneous nanocatalyst-based magnetic polyaniline decorated with cobalt oxide., 319,123858.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2022.123858>.
- 7) Banerjee, S.; Rout, S.; Banerjee, S.; Atta, A.; Das, D. J. E. C.(2019), Management, Fe₂O₃ nanocatalyst aided transesterification for biodiesel production from lipid-intact wet microalgal biomass: a biorefinery approach. , 195, 844-853.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2019.05.060>.
- 8) Corrales-Pérez, B.; Vicente, G.; del Puerto Morales, M.; Gallo-Cordova, A. J. F.,(2024), Magnetic induction heating-assisted synthesis of biodiesel using an alumina/iron oxide nanocatalyst., 368, 131659.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2024.131659>.
- 9) David A. Wood, (2021). Microalgae to biodiesel - Review of recent progress, Bioresource Technology Reports, 14,100665, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biteb.2021.100665>.
- 10) Digambar Singh, Dilip Sharma, S.L. Soni, Sumit Sharma, Pushpendra Kumar Sharma, Amit Jhalani, (2020). A review on feedstocks, production processes, and yield for different generations of biodiesel, Fuel, 262,116553. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2019.116553>
- 11) Farooq Anwar, Maria Tariq, Jan Nisar, Ghulam Ali, Humaira Kanwal (2023), Optimization of biodiesel yield from non-food karanja seed oil: Characterisation and assessment of fuel properties, Sustainable Chemistry for the Environment,3,100035. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scenv.2023.100035>.
- 12) Gincy Marina Mathew, Diksha Raina, Vivek Narisetty, Vinod Kumar, Saurabh Saran, Arivalagan Pugazhendi, Raveendran Sindhu, Ashok Pandey, Parameswaran Binod (2021),Recent advances in biodiesel production: Challenges and solutions, Science of The Total Environment, 794,2021,148751, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.148751>.
- 13) Hussain, J.; Ali, Z. M.; Shah, F. A.; Qadeer, A.; Laghari, A. N.; Sohil, M. J. J. o. E. E.,(2025), Facile synthesis and catalytic evaluation of iron-doped zinc oxide nanocatalysts for biodiesel production. , 26 (10), 352-359 <https://doi.org/10.12911/22998993/206962>.
- 14) Jolius Gimbun, Mohd Affandi Mohd Ali, Cheng Kui Cheng, Sumaiya Zainal Abidin, Maizirwan Mel, Siew Choo Chin (2025, Elucidating the clinker-based catalyst deactivation for biodiesel production in a continuous microwave-assisted reactor,Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering, 13, (1),115186,<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2024.115186>.
- 15) Mansi H. Magar, Vishnu A. Adole, Manohar R. Patil, Ravindra H. Waghchaure, Umesh J. Tupe, Thansing B. Pawar (2024), Fabrication of modified Sb₂O₃ nanospheres for the removal of hazardous malachite green organic pollutant and selective NO₂ gas sensor, Journal of the Indian Chemical Society,101, (11),101396, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jics.2024.101396>.

- 16) Marjorie Morales, Claude Aflalo, Olivier Bernard (2021), Microalgal lipids: A review of lipids' potential and quantification for 95 phytoplankton species, *Biomass and Bioenergy*,150, 106108, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2021.106108>.
- 17) Mohammed Takase (2022)., Biodiesel Yield and Conversion Percentage from Waste Frying Oil Using Fish Shell at Elmina as a Heterogeneous Catalyst and the Kinetics of the Reaction, *Hindawi International Journal of Chemical Engineering* , 1-9, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/8718638>.
- 18) Krishna Prasad Shrestha, Binod Raj Giri, Ronan Pelé, Khalid Aljohani, Pierre Brequigny, Fabian Mauss, Fabien Halter, Lam K. Huynh, Christine Mounaïm-Rousselle (2025). A comprehensive chemical kinetic modelling and experimental study of NH₃-methanol/ethanol combustion towards net-zero CO₂ emissions, *Combustion and Flame*, 274,113954. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2024.113954>.
- 19) Patil, N. M., Huse, N. P., & Patil, M. R. (2025). Synthesis of CuFe₂O₄ Nanoparticles for Applications in Biodiesel Production and Degradation of Methylene Blue Dye. *Iranian Journal of Catalysis*, <https://doi.org/10.57647/j.ijc.2025.1503.32>.
- 20) Patil, N.M., Patil, M.R., Marathe, Y.V. *et al.*(2025). Investigating emission characteristics nano particle added *spirogyra* algae based biodiesel blends using ML techniques. *Environ Dev Sustain* . <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-025-06520-w>.
- 21) Rakesh Kumar Sharma, Rakeshwar Bandichhor, Vishwesh Mishra, Shivani Sharma, Sneha Yadav ,Shilpa Mehta ,(2023). Bhavya Arora , Pooja Rana, Sriparna Dutta and Kanika Solanki, Advanced metal oxide-based nanocatalysts for the oxidative synthesis of fine chemicals, *Mater. Adv.*, 2023, **4**, 1795-1830, DOI: [10.1039/D2MA00977C](https://doi.org/10.1039/D2MA00977C).
- 22) Steinbach, Julia C. Fait, Fabio Mayer, Hermann A, Kandelbauer (2023).Andreas Sol-Gel-Controlled Size and Morphology of Mesoporous Silica Microspheres Using Hard Templates. 8(33), <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.3c03098>.
- 23) Seyed Ali Hosseini (2022), Nanocatalysts for biodiesel production, *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 15, (10),104152, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2022.104152>.
- 24) Salaheldeen, M., Mariod, A. A., Aroua, M. K., Rahman, S. M. A., Soudagar, M. E. M., & Fattah, I. M. R. (2021). Current State and Perspectives on Transesterification of Triglycerides for Biodiesel Production. *Catalysts*, 11(9), 1121. <https://doi.org/10.3390/catal11091121>.
- 25) S. Chozhavendhan, M. Vijay Pradhap Singh, B. Fransila, R. Praveen Kumar, G. Karthiga Devi (2020), A review on influencing parameters of biodiesel production and purification processes, *Current Research in Green and Sustainable Chemistry*,1-2,1-6, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crgsc.2020.04.002>.

- 26) Xia, S.; Li, J.; Chen, G.; Tao, J.; Li, W.; Zhu, G. J. R. E., (2022) Magnetic reusable acid-base bifunctional Co doped $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-CaO}$ nanocatalysts for biodiesel production from soybean oil and waste frying oil. , 189, 421-434.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.02.122>.
- 27) Xia, S.; Li, J.; Chen, G.; Tao, J.; Li, W.; Zhu, G. J. R. E., (2022), Magnetic reusable acid-base bifunctional Co doped $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-CaO}$ nanocatalysts for biodiesel production from soybean oil and waste frying oil. 189, 421-434.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.02.122>.
- 28) Wan Nur Aisyah Wan Osman, Mohd Hakimi Rosli, Wan Nur Athirah Mazli, Shafirah Samsuri, (2024).Comparative review of biodiesel production and purification, Carbon Capture Science & Technology,13 ,100264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccsst.2024.100264>.

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